

Student Engagement with Online and Digital Library Services in a Federal University Setting

ONWUBIKO Emmanuel Chidiadi

Alex Ekwueme Federal University, Ikwo, Nigeria

ORCID: 0000-0001-9386-4972

onwubikoemma@yahoo.com or emmabikos@gmail.com

ABSTRACT

The rapid advancements in information and communication Technology (ICT) and the dynamics of globalization have brought about tremendous transformation in the ways things are done and information acquired, and handled across various industries, organizations, institutions and bodies as well as other fields of human endeavors and knowledge acquisitions and libraries especially academic libraries are said to be at the epicenter. This study took cognizance of this development to assess the online and digital information services provided by a given university library to her student-users with a view to identifying the challenges and ways to improving the website for effective online information service delivery to student-users and by extension all users. The study applied a descriptive survey design and was guided by four research questions formulated in line with the research objectives. The sampled population for the study was 640 students who were in three and four hundred levels of the Faculties of Education, Social Sciences, and Medical Sciences, Art/Humanities as well as Faculties of law and Basic medical Science and 20 librarians/library officers through purposive sampling technique. While the student-respondents provided answers in respect of objective 1, the librarians provided answers for objectives 2 and 3. A four point Likert type structured questionnaire was the only instrument used for data collection. The instrument was validated using Cronbach's alpha. Result showed coefficient of $\alpha=0.80$. Data collected were analyzed using frequencies, simple percentile and statistical mean and presented in tables. The outcome of the study did reveal that the library of Alex Ekwueme Federal University does provide some online and digital information services such as online information literacy instruction, online reference services and online public access catalogue (OPAC) and at the same time, falls short in the provision of some other notable online and digital services as in the areas of online courses and Remote access to online catalogue and that poor internet connectivity, inadequate funding of the library among others are major factors militating against the library from providing effective online and digital information services to the students. It further found that to enhance the library website for effective online information service delivery to her users, the library should among other things provide a single point of access to library resources and library online services should be operational 24 hours every day and every week (24/7). Based on the findings, the study suggested that inter-alia that the university management with the support of the federal government, should provide adequate fund to enable the library acquire all needed ICT facilities and equipment that will heighten the provision of online and digital information services to the library users while the librarians on their part, should be more committed to delivering online information services to the users through acquiring the desirable skills and knowledge.

Keywords: Online Information Service, Digital Ecosystem, University Library, Information and Communication Technology, Digital Information Service, Student-Users

Mathematics Subject Classification [MSC] Number: 62P25, 62P99

1.0. INTRODUCTION

The rapid advancements in information and communication Technology (ICT) and the dynamics of globalization have brought about tremendous transformation in the ways things are done and information acquired and handled across various industries, organizations, institutions and bodies as

well as other fields of human endeavors and knowledge acquisitions and libraries especially academic libraries are said to be at the epicenter. This is because academic libraries serve as information hub of the parent institutions fostering teaching, learning and research. The integration of ICT in academic library services has not only enhanced the way information is acquired, processed, stored and disseminated but has also enhanced users experiences and expanded access to information in innovative ways.

ICT which cut across, computers, digital system, databases, multimedia technologies, storage devices and platforms, communication system, and the internet among others is an embodiment of all forms of technologies and systems that are applied and used for information management. As noted by Elegbede (2016), no country in the world from developed climes like UK, USA, china and Malaysia to other developing countries like Nigeria, there is absolutely no sector of the economy that are operating effectively with application and use of ICT. The underlying issue is that it has assumed a significant position in the affairs of man across the global ecosystem. It is against this backdrop that one today hears of e-banking, e-banking, e-billing, e-commerce, e-payment, e-governance, e-business, e-libraries, e-libraries and their likes. Evidence available reveals that the adoption, application and utilization of ICTs and social media in our educational system more so tertiary institutions are the order of the era. The assertion is that for many, the ICTs and the internet are becoming embedded part of everyday life and are seen as indispensable commodity for socialization, communication and business transaction, sharpening several aspects of human existence, not leaving out fast developing regions like Africa. With ubiquity of digital technologies on the continents, it is common to find more than a few individuals with mobile phones- smart or dull computer systems, among other gadgets across urban and rural centres (Elegbede, 2016).

In addition to the above assertion, the ability to master relevant skills on digital devices, processes and systems that will positively affects one's life, career, business and future towards prime productivity, through efficient time and resource management connote digital literacy. It is the pathway to acquiring essential digital skills, the path to developing digital individuals with dexterity, creating digital jobs and workforce and eventually building a digital economy which thrives on the advances of digital technologies. It is therefore not surprising reveals Emezue and Nwohiri (2013) that students and faculty have developed greater preference for electronic information systems and services than manually driven ones and this is as a result of the availability of digital information which has caused users to find alternative means of study and research with the aid of laptops, smart phones, tablets and other related digital technologies.

In the Nigerian context, it seems that many libraries and information centres, academic libraries inclusive operations and services are not actually in tandem with the reality of the digital era. A development that is against the thought of Gbaji (2007) that transporting library services to the online environment for the Nigerian academic libraries in the digital age are enormous particularly with the dynamic nature of digital technology which constantly creating the need for new skills , work environment, work methods, since librarians are the link between information and the users. The above assertion is also in tandem with the stand of Abubakar (2011) that digital revolution has dramatically

changed the face of libraries in the 21st century and this is a clarion call for academic libraries in Nigeria to digitize their services and resources through appropriate ICT applications if they are to remain relevant. This is in view of the fact that users of academic libraries in this digital era are mostly students and they are perceived as digital natives and citizens of next generation. Suffice to say, that these student-clients stand out as principle users and to a large extent, rely on computing, digital and online technologies for addressing their life issues which include education and training programs, regardless of the position of Baro, Endouware, and Ubogu (2013) that majority of the students are not aware and do not use the online information resources.

No matter the way it is looked at, information has become a vital national and global resource that determine the direction of any nation globally. To this end noted Abbas (2014), librarians, information professionals and documentalists must be conversant with the emerging information and communication technologies for effective organization and destination of information with a view to enhancing knowledge. This implies that it behooves academic libraries and their librarians to deliver effective online and digital information services to students of their parent institutions. Information services so to speak is used as an umbrella term to describe a heterogeneous group of individual, social and institutional forms of helping people to know more, or to cross and bend their boundaries of knowing (Science Direct, 2012). While to Chatterjee (2017) the term information service refers to any service which is intended to provide information for a client or user, or assist a client or user in finding information which may include any service rendered by a library or information center such as reference service and even document lending service. On the other hand, in the context of librarianship and information science online and digital information service may be defined as those digital based or virtual services provided to users regardless of location. This implies that the users are bona-fide registered members of the library with such services facilitated with library functional website and portals under the control of digital librarians.

It is also referred to as the provision of electronic information resources by libraries through the purchase or subscription of large datasets from external vendors, allowing users to access a wide range of databases hosted on servers for a fee. The availability of such website with up to date information resources will facilitate the provision of online information services to users. Elegbede (2016) listed such online services to include, digital reference services, online selective dissemination of information (e-SDI), online current awareness services (e-CAS), online document delivery services, online literature search services, online referral services, digital translation services as well as online user education and information literacy programs while Emezie and Nwaohiri (2013) added, advocacy, use of social media, mobile phones, information packaging and repackaging, quality reference services and partnership with other academic units for information literacy programs. According to Gbaje and Kotso (2014), for any library website to be effective to meet the information needs of her clientele, it must conform to certain best practices which include inter-alia, providing single point of access to library resources and facilitating access to library and information services remotely.

Inasmuch as some factors such as librarians inadequate competency, lack of technology literacy, poor internet connectivity inadequate power supply and poor funding (Emezie & Nwaohiri (2013) have been

attributed to hindering provision of information services to users, one cannot deny the fact that some academic libraries are making remarkable efforts at ensuring that they move in line with the emerging technologies by at least computerizing their routine services such as acquisitions, processing, charging and discharging and serials management then, developing online cataloguing and other retrieval aids, creating institutional repository, developing library website, providing online information services among other. On the other hand, there are some that are still sitting on the fence and still rely on traditional methods of information services delivery and appear less perturbed even with little or no patronage.

It is in view of this, that this study is embarked upon as to ascertain the type of online and digital information services provisions to students of Alex Ekwueme Federal University, Ikwo, Ebonyi State Nigeria considering the fact that no such study has been carried out, an indication that there is a gap in knowledge that needs to be filled. In this regard, the general objectives of this study are:

- i. To ascertain the types of online and digital information services provided by Alex Ekwueme Federal University library to students,
- ii. To determine challenges faced by the library in her efforts to providing effective online information delivery services to the students and
- iii. To identify Factors that can enhance effective and efficient library website for online information services delivery

Research Questions

The study is guided by the following research questions:

- i. What digital and online services are provided for students of Alex Ekwueme Federal University, Ikwo, Nigeria by the university library?
- ii. What are the challenges hindering the university library in providing effective online information services to the students?
- iii. What best practices do you think the library website should conform to be effective in meeting the information needs of the students?

2.0. Methodology

The study applied a descriptive survey design and was guided by three research questions formulated in line with the research objectives. The sampled population for the study was 640 students who were in three and four hundred levels of the Faculties of Education, Social Sciences, and Medical Sciences, Art/Humanities as well as Faculties of law and Basic medical Science and 20 librarians/library officers through purposive sampling technique. While the student-respondents provided answers in respect of objective 1, the librarians provided answers for objectives 2 and 3. A four point Likert type structured questionnaire was the only instrument used for data collection. The instrument was validated by three experts from the department of measurement and evaluation of Abia State University, Uturu, Nigeria

using Cronbach's alpha. Result showed coefficient of $\alpha=0.80$. The questionnaires were personally administered by the researcher to the respondents and were 100% returned. Data collected were analyzed using frequencies, simple percentile and statistical mean and presented in tables.

3.0. PRESENTATION OF RESULTS

Table 1: Types of online and digital information services provided by Alex Ekwueme Federal University library to students,

Items	SA		A		DA		SDA		Mean (X)
	F	%	F	%	F	%	F	%	
Online information literacy instruction	480	75	30	4.69	70	10.94	60	9.37	3.45
Online courses	***	***	***	***	***	***	680	100	1.00
Online reference services	330	51.56	190	29.69	70	10.94	50	7.81	3.25
Remote access to online catalogue	***	***	***	***	130	20.31	510	79.69	1.20
Weblog	410	64.06	93	14.53	36	5.62	101	15.78	3.27
Online document delivery	230	35.94	181	28.28	109	17.03	120	18.75	2.81
OPAC	640	100	***	***	***	***	***	***	4.00
Access to e-journals	640	100	***	***	***	***	***	***	4.00
Access to e-books	640	100	***	***	***	***	***	***	4.00
E-user education	***	***	***	***	300	46.87	340	53.13	1.47
Library website	640	100	***	***	***	***	***	***	4.00
Internet services	610	95.31	30	4.69	***	***	***	***	3.95
Intranet services	***	***	***	***	190	29.69	450	70.31	1.29

*Key: SA=Strongly Agree, A=Agree, DA=Disagree, SDA=Strongly Disagree

Benchmark=2.50

Table 1 contains data on types of online services provided by the library of Alex Ekwueme Federal University to the student users. 610 respondents which represent 100% strongly agree that the library provides the following online services, online public access catalogue (OPAC), e-journals, e-books and operational website with statistical Mean (X) of 4.00 respectively, while 640 or 95.31% strongly agree and 4.69% or 30 respondents also agree that the library provides internet services with a Mean (X) of 3.95. Other online services being provided by the libraries with over 500 of the respondents strongly agree or agree are, online information literacy instruction, Weblog, Online reference services and online document delivery with their Mean (X) ranging from 2.81 to 3.45 above the benchmark of 2.50. On the other hand, series such as Online courses, Remote access to online catalogue, Intranet services and e-user education fall below the benchmark of 2.50 as the entire 640 respondents represent 100%

strongly disagree or disagree of the provision of such services by the library with benchmark ranging from 1.00 to 1.47.

Table 2: militating factors against library and librarians providing effective online information delivery services to the students

Items	SA		A		DA		SDA		Mean (X)
	F	%	F	%	F	%	F	%	
Lack of basic digital skills	***	***	***	***	8	40	12	60	1.4
Librarians incompetency	***	***	***	***	8	40	12	60	1.4
Lack of technology literacy on the part of the students	4	20	3	15	***	***	13	65	1.9
Poor internet connectivity	20	100	***	***	***	***	***	***	4.00
Leadership	12	60	4	20	***	***	4	20	3.2
Misplacement of priority by university management	2	10	3	15	2	10	13	65	1.7
Inadequate funding of the Library	20	100	***	***	***	***	***	***	4.00
Epileptic power supply	20	100	***	***	***	***	***	***	4.00
Poor information and communication technology infrastructure in the country	20	100	***	***	***	***	***	***	4.00
Underdeveloped virtual libraries and online system in Nigeria	20	100	***	***	***	***	***	***	4.00

*Key: SA=Strongly Agree, A=Agree, DA=Disagree, SDA=Strongly Disagree

Benchmark=2.50

Data as collected and displayed in table 2 above did reveal that the 20 respondents or 100% who are librarians and library officers in the library under study, strongly agree that Poor internet connectivity, Inadequate funding of the library, epileptic power supply, poor information and communication technology infrastructure in the country and underdeveloped virtual libraries and online system in Nigeria with mean of 4.00 respectively are major factors militating against library and librarians providing effective online information delivery services to the students while 12 of the 20 respondents representing 60% strongly agree and another 4 respondents or 20% agree with a statistical of 3.20 that leadership is one of the major challenges. Whereas, items like Lack of basic digital skills, Librarians incompetency, Misplacement of priority by university management and Lack of technology literacy on the part of the students were not considered as challenges as they hand statistical mean ranging from 1.4 to 1.9 which are below the benchmark of 2.50 leading to the being rejected as parts of the challenges.

Table 3: Factors that can enhance effective and efficient library website for online information services delivery to students

Items	SA		A		DA		SDA		Mean (X)
	F	%	F	%	F	%	F	%	
Provision of a single point of access to library resources	640	100	***	***	***	***	***	***	4.00
The library website should be designed as to allowing lecturers direct students to useful resources with ease	640	100	***	***	***	***	***	***	4.00
University library should promote help library digital resources	640	100	***	***	***	***	***	***	4.00
Navigating library resources online should be made easy	640	100	***	***	***	***	***	***	4.00
There should be easy and efficient access to e-resources	640	100	***	***	***	***	***	***	4.00
There should be facilitation of library and information services remotely	640	100	***	***	***	***	***	***	4.00
Library online services should be 24/7	640	100	***	***	***	***	***	***	4.00
There should be separate website for each faculty	40	6.25	10	1.56	***	***	590	92.19	1.22

*Key: SA=Strongly Agree, A=Agree, DA=Disagree, SDA=Strongly Disagree

Benchmark=2.50

As shown in table 3, the 640 which is 100% respondents strongly agree that to enhance effective and efficient library website for online information services delivery to students, the library should Provide a single point of access to library resources, library online services should be 24/7, the library website should be designed as to allowing lecturers direct students to useful resources with ease, the library should promote help library digital resources, Navigating library resources online should be made easy, as well as that there should be easy and efficient access to e-resources and there should be facilitation of library and information services with all enjoying 4.00 statistical mean, while, 590 respondents or 92.19 with a mean of 1.22 strongly disagree to the idea of separate website for each faculty against 40 or 10% that indicated in favor.

4.0. DISCUSSION OF FINDINGS

The findings of this study in the first instance did reveal that the library of Alex Ekwueme Federal University do provide some online and digital information services such as online information literacy

instruction, online reference services, weblog, online document delivery, online public access catalogue (OPAC), e-journals, e-books and operational website and at the same time, falls short in the provision of some other notable university libraries online and digital services as in the areas of Online courses, Remote access to online catalogue, E-user education and Intranet services. The outcome of this study in this area is that of a mixed feeling as it's neither here nor there. These online and digital services as provided by the library fall below expectations as highlighted by Elegbede (2016) that such online services will include, digital reference services, online selective dissemination of information (e-SDI), online current awareness services (e-CAS), online document delivery services, online literature search services, online referral services, digital translation services as well as online user education and information literacy programs and the addendum of Emezie and Nwaohiri (2013) that online services of any university library should include, advocacy, use of social media, mobile phones, information packaging and repackaging, quality reference services and partnership with other academic units for information literacy programs.

The study further discovered that poor internet connectivity, inadequate funding of the library, epileptic power supply, poor information and communication technology infrastructure in the country and underdeveloped virtual libraries and online system in Nigeria are major factors militating against the library of Alex Ekwueme Federal University and her librarians from providing effective online and digital information services to the students as well as poor leadership qualities of head of the university management. This outcome no doubt agrees with the assertion of (Emezie & Nwaohiri (2013) that factors such as librarians inadequate competency, lack of technology literacy, poor internet connectivity inadequate power supply and poor funding have been attributed to hindering provision of information services to users but noted that one cannot deny the fact that some academic libraries are making remarkable efforts at ensuring that they move in line with the emerging technologies by at least computerizing their routine services such as acquisitions, processing, charging and discharging and serials management then, developing online cataloguing and other retrieval aids, creating institutional repository, developing library website, providing online information services among others. The later may be said to be in the altruism as in the case of the library of Alex Ekwueme Federal University as it is actually providing some online and digital services to the student users as noted in table 1.

It was also discovered that some ways to enhance effective and efficient library website for online information services delivery to the students by the library will be through providing a single point of access to library resources, library online services being operational 24 hours every day and every week (24/7), the library website being designed in such a way as to allowing lecturers direct students to useful resources with ease, the library promoting help library digital resources, Navigating library resources online been made easy, as well as easy and efficient access to e-resources and facilitation of library and information services. This result is in conformity with the proposition of Gbaje and Kotso (2014) that for any library website to be effective to meet the information needs of her clientele, it must conform to certain best practices which include inter-alia, providing single point of access to library resources and facilitating access to library and information services remotely.

5.0. CONCLUSION AND RECOMMENDATIONS

The inference based on the findings of this study are that the said university studied is providing online and digital information services to her student users but the services are not all that encompassing as it is only providing online information literacy instruction, online reference services, weblog, online document delivery, online public access catalogue (OPAC), e-journals, e-books and operational website to the users therefore much needs to be done by the library (going by the list of online and digital services streamlined for university libraries) to enhance their online services to the students and by extension other users of the library and that there are many factors inhibiting the library and librarians from providing effective online information delivery services to the student users which include, epileptic power supply, poor information and communication technology infrastructure in the country and underdeveloped virtual libraries and online system in Nigeria. Furthermore, that there are various way to enhancing not exclusively Alex Ekwueme Federal university library but every other university library website which include through providing a single point of access to library resources, library online services being operational 24 hours every day and every week (24/7), the library website been designed in such a way as to allowing lecturers direct students to useful resources with ease, the library promoting help library digital resources, navigating library resources online been made easy, as well as designing the site in such a way that it allow easy and efficient access to e-resources.

Suffice to say, that the library needs to add more peep as to living up to the expectations of the users in this digital era as users will stop at demanding for online information services as it is the preference as far as the 21st century is concerned and beyond because that is what is trending. This implies that a university library like Alex Ekwueme Federal University, should wake to the reality on ground and do the needful by employing all desirable technological facilities and tools as to be better positioned to satisfying the information needs of her teeming student users and by extension all users in this digital ecosystem to enable them enjoy to the fullest the gains of digital globalization powered by ICT and ruled by digital information. In this regard, the following suggestions are put forward for consideration:

1. The university management with the support of the federal government, should provide adequate fund to enable the library acquire all needed ICT facilities and equipment that will heighten the provision of online and digital information services to the library users while the librarians on their part, should be more committed to delivering online information services to the users through acquiring the desirable skills and knowledge in line with any trending ICT as to still remain relevant in this global digital ecosystem.
2. The library should be totally powered with solar system instead of relying on hydro-power energy which has remained a nightmare to Nigerians and an institution like the university library cannot rely on such, if it is to effectively and efficiently provide online and digital information services to her users.
3. Since the website is the stronghold of every online information services, the library management should ensure that the library website is designed in line with the suggestions given by the respondents as displayed in table 3 of this study.

4. The effectiveness of an online information service is an uninterrupted internet provision. To this end, the library management with the support of the university management should see it as a necessity as to ensuring regular subscription of needed data from the internet providers (IPs) preferably, the library should go WI-FI.
5. The Nigerian government should come up with virtual library consortium managed by experts that will facilitate the development of virtual libraries and online system in Nigeria which will also help university libraries share digital resources among themselves as well as government being focused and determined to change the narrative of poor information and communication technology infrastructure in the country for the better.
6. Nigeria backwardness generally is as a result of not having the right leaders and university libraries and the entirety of Nigerian universities are no exemption as they stand as the microcosm of the macrocosm called Nigeria. The way forward is that a round peg should be placed in a round hole and not the other way round. The implication is that, well trained leader librarians with tested and trusted leadership qualities should be appointed to head any university library and not political appointees who are only there to enrich themselves.

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